

Self-Weight Consolidation Process of Water-Saturated Deltas on Mars and Earth

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Contents of this file

Tables S1 to S5

Introduction

Table S1 is the original data of the measurements of the moisture content w_0 , **Table S2** is the original data of the pycnometer test, which was conducted to obtain the specific gravity G_s of our samples, **Table S3** is the original data of the consolidation experiments, **Table S4** is the original data of the permeability experiments, and **Table S5** is the martian global delta relief obtained by us based on MOLA data, which is used as the maximum thickness of a delta.

Table S1. The original data of the measurements of the moisture content w_0 . The initial void ratio is calculated by equation (1). A' is the inner area of the consolidation container.

Parallel groups	Dry mass m_d (g)	Wet mass m_0 (g)	Water mass m_w ($=m_0-m_d$) (g)	Inner area (A') (cm^2)	Sample's height (L) (cm)	Bulk volume ($V= A'L$) (cm^3)	Bulk density (ρ_0) (g/cm^3)	Moisture content (w_0)	Initial void ratio (e_0)
1	190	246.9	56.9	30	4	120	2.0575	29.95	0.8568
2	190	251.5	61.5	30	4	120	2.0958	32.37	0.8568
3	188.5	247.3	58.8	30	4	120	2.0608	31.19	0.8716

Table S2 The original data of the pycnometer test, which was conducted to obtain the specific gravity G_s of our samples. The specific gravity G_s can be derived from:

$$G_s = \frac{m_d}{m_{bw}+m_d-m_{bws}} G_{wT} \quad (\text{S22})$$

Where m_d is the samples' dry mass, m_{bw} is the total mass of the pycnometer and water, m_{bws} is the total mass of the pycnometer, water and samples, and G_{wT} is the specific gravity of pure water at $T^\circ\text{C}$.

m_d (g)	m_{bw} (g)	m_{bws} (g)	G_{wT} (g)
15.0474	157.5095	167.4430	0.998

Table S3. The original data of consolidation experiments of our samples. The void ratio is calculated by equation (2).

Load increment order	Vertical effective stress (σ') (kPa)	Parallel Groups	Accumulated settlement amount ($\sum\Delta h_i$) (mm)	Samples' Initial height (h_0) (mm)	Void ratio (e)
1	50	1	0.133	40	0.8506
		2	0.308	40	0.8425
		3	0.3	40	0.8576
2	100	1	0.174	40	0.8487
		2	1.761	40	0.7751
		3	0.36	40	0.8548

3	200	1	0.508	40	0.8332
		2	1.835	40	0.7716
		3	0.51	40	0.8477
4	400	1	0.975	40	0.8115
		2	2.191	40	0.7551
		3	0.84	40	0.8323
5	800	1	1.749	40	0.7756
		2	2.449	40	0.7431
		3	1.84	40	0.7855
6	1200	1	2.369	40	0.7468
		2	2.755	40	0.7289
		3	2.70	40	0.7453
7	1600	1	3.026	40	0.7163
		2	4.273	40	0.6584
		3	3.33	40	0.7158
8	2400	1	4.113	40	0.6659
		2	4.951	40	0.6270
		3	4.61	40	0.6559
9	3200	1	5.036	40	0.6230
		2	6.305	40	0.5641
		3	5.77	40	0.6016

Table S4. The original data of permeability experiments of our samples. The hydraulic conductivity K was calculated by equations (3) and (4). The inner area A' of the consolidation container is 30 cm^2 , the cross-sectional area a' of the water pipe is 0.89286 cm^2 , and the seepage path length L equals the sample initial height h_0 minus the accumulated height $\sum \Delta h_i$. t_1 and t_2 are the first and the second test results of time-taken for water dropping from H_1 to H_2 , respectively. t is the average of t_1 and t_2 . T' is the temperature during the experiments. Note: we only test the T' of the third group and here we used the average of T' ($=12.5^\circ\text{C}$) to represent the temperature of all three parallel groups during the experiments. It's acceptable because T' varies slightly throughout the experiments, whose fluctuations hardly affect the order of magnitude of the hydraulic conductivity K . The seepage velocity $v=Q/A't$, in which Q is the volume of water that seeps out of the samples.

Load increment order	Vertical effective stress (σ') (kPa)	Parallel groups	Initial water head (H_1) (m)	Final water head (H_2) (m)	Time1 (t_1) (s)	Time2 (t_2) (s)	Average time ($t=(t_1+t_2)/2$) (s)	Seepage Velocity (v) (cm/s)	T' ($^\circ\text{C}$)
1	50	1	93	38	7.77	8.39	8.08	0.2026	-
		2	93	38	7.67	7.77	7.72	0.212	-

		3	93	38	8.41	8.6	8.505	0.1925	10
2	100	1	93	38	8.51	8.9	8.705	0.188	-
		2	93	38	7.68	8.23	7.955	0.2058	-
		3	93	38	9.03	9.1	9.065	0.1806	14
3	200	1	93	38	9.11	9.78	9.445	0.1733	-
		2	93	38	8.39	9	8.695	0.1883	-
		3	93	38	9.11	9.12	9.115	0.1796	14
4	400	1	93	38	11.3	11.4	11.35	0.1442	-
		2	93	38	8.71	9.3	9.005	0.1818	-
		3	93	38	9.17	9.24	9.205	0.1778	10
5	800	1	93	38	11.4	11.6	11.5	0.1423	-
		2	93	38	8.87	8.09	8.48	0.193	-
		3	93	38	9.36	9.44	9.4	0.1741	14
6	1200	1	93	38	11.7	12	11.85	0.1381	-
		2	93	38	9.5	9.35	9.425	0.1737	-
		3	93	38	10.37	10.52	10.445	0.1567	10
7	1600	1	93	38	12.5	13.3	12.9	0.1269	-
		2	93	38	12.3	11.5	11.9	0.1376	-
		3	93	38	12.2	12.73	12.465	0.1313	14
8	2400	1	93	38	12.1	12.1	12.1	0.1353	-
		2	93	38	17.1	16.9	17	0.0963	-
		3	93	38	15.38	20.64	18.01	0.0909	13
9	3200	1	93	38	14.6	15	14.8	0.1106	-
		2	93	38	27	27.7	27.35	0.0599	-
		3	93	38	36.35	36.59	36.47	0.0449	14

Table S5. The delta relief of a delta. The locations of martian deltas are based on the database of Wilson et al. (2021)

Delta Label (name)	Apex Latitude, N	Apex Longitude, E	Delta Relief (km)
1	-53.51	-149.16	0.462
2	-53.13	-14.33	0.082
3	-39.15	-103.07	0.694
4	-35.49	-86.49	0.32
5	-32.39	103	0.404
6	-30.68	35.85	0.267
7	-30.59	32.71	0.134
8	-29.25	84.55	0.29
9	-28.57	-50.44	0.319
10	-28.52	-50.45	0.528

11	-28.01	83.08	0.299
12	-23.82	-33.73	0.152
13	-23.61	-23.76	0.058
14	-22.4	-23.7	0.173
15	-22.35	36.97	0.328
16	-22.1	-47.61	0.46
17	-21.64	57.27	0.208
18	-19.35	12.85	0.113
19	-18.92	26.55	0.516
20	-15.68	-155.21	0.235
21	-11.38	139.51	0.174
22	-10.91	154.47	0.127
23	-10.46	144.57	0.258
24	-10.4	144.79	0.122
25	-9.85	-53.44	0.25
26	-9.74	148.79	0.408
27	-9.17	149.73	0.422
28	-8.63	-159.26	0.46
29	-8	-146.57	0.448
30	-6.57	141.12	1.4
31	-6.27	-149.49	0.184
32	-5.83	137.19	0.218
33	-5.48	136.97	0.142
34	-5.47	136.07	0.224
35	-5.01	136.71	0.382
36	-4.99	136.74	0.496
37	-4.59	117.98	0.197
38	-4.14	-51.83	0.239
39	-1.28	-41.03	0.239
40	1.4	116.2	0.39
41	2.14	121.61	0.672
42	2.73	-51.67	0.351
43	4.19	-38.71	0.292
44	5.09	-58.63	0.302
45	7.57	-38.97	0.568
46	7.86	-26.15	0.082
47	8.17	-55.13	0.464
48	8.44	-49.74	0.783
49	8.49	-48.01	0.082
50	8.63	-50.68	0.143
51	8.98	-15.78	0.79
52	9.58	-46.23	0.441
53	11.35	-51.29	0.259
54	11.66	-47.01	0.024

55	11.71	-52.97	0.46
56	12.87	43.12	0.139
57	13.33	8.9	0.667
58	14.05	-24.31	0.075
59	14.55	-51.77	0.243
60	16.05	-53.23	0.502
61	18.2	-169.54	0.204
62	18.31	-169.65	0.452
63	18.5	77.32	0.156
64	19.64	11.72	0.725
65	21.03	75.54	0.727
66	22.05	-22.94	0.183
67	22.46	-8.49	0.146
68	22.55	-8.38	0.284
69	24.09	-20.71	0.187
70	24.15	-177.14	0.097
71	25.78	56.8	0.632
72	26.38	74.48	0.199
73	26.42	74.19	0.364
74	26.46	56.94	0.719
75	26.94	76.04	0.888
76	27.61	21.25	0.414
77	27.68	11.24	0.504
78	27.9	11.1	0.534
79	27.98	11.1	0.749
80	28.06	27.13	0.325
81	28.13	11.21	0.544
82	28.25	11.44	0.464
83	28.45	-12.25	0.376
84	29.41	25.73	0.306
85	29.44	56.88	0.302
86	30.47	162.61	0.227
87	30.71	65.8	1.208
88	30.9	12.31	0.069
89	31.15	17.16	0.471
90	31.31	-0.13	0.21
91	31.64	-13.17	0.51
92	31.81	5.96	0.444
93	31.95	20.65	0.412
94	32.67	7.05	0.045
95	33.23	-11.15	0.486
96	33.32	-54.94	0.163
97	33.39	2.45	0.613
98	33.42	-10.06	0.074

99	33.63	3.57	0.427
100	33.67	6.92	0.151
101	33.86	4.14	0.327
102	33.95	17.58	0.476
103	35.02	6.5	0.592
104	35.14	-55.54	0.042
105	35.31	-9.36	0.165
106	35.43	32.56	0.068
107	35.48	-11.94	0.135
108	35.48	32.61	0.146
109	35.81	0.74	0.208
110	35.85	0.4	0.537
111	35.86	0.51	0.322
112	36.64	36.35	0.136
113	37.2	1.66	0.228
114	37.35	-1.92	0.072
